

Teachers' Participation in Curriculum Development Process

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Abstract

Curriculum development is an integral part of education system has a varying meanings and interpretations. The development of curriculum is a value laden process of determining what should be taught within the institutions or schools. Social, cultural, political, and geographical context has the major influences on curriculum design and development everywhere. Teachers' participation in curriculum development was the topic of this study. The main purpose of this study is to explore the teachers' perception of curriculum development process, their concept of curriculum itself and their ownership of the curriculum. This study is based on interpretive paradigm. The qualitative approach of this study was descriptive and exploratory based on the narrative inquiry. I have tried to include three teachers of community school from the different parts of Chitwan. Consistent with qualitative methodology, teachers' perceptions of curriculum development process were explored through in-depth interviews, observation and analysis of documents. Primary information was collected via in-depth interview and observation to this study. I have tried to interpret the field data by giving appropriate meaning to the persons' stories which represent and visualize the field data by the help of narration of different theories and themes are directly linked to my research questions and objectives. Findings of study is that participating teachers were perceive curriculum development process as impractical and centrally dominated.

Keywords: Curriculum, Curriculum Development, Curriculum Development Process, Teachers' Participation, Perception of Teacher

Introduction

'Curriculum' is a word repeatedly used in education with different meanings, definitions and levels of development. Every nation has certain standards of curriculum development and is developed by the teams of teachers and administrators at the local or national level. Whatever be the process of development of the curriculum that is directly associated with the classroom teacher.

Before one can understand curriculum development process, one needs to understand the meaning and definition of

curriculum. The knowledge of curriculum is important for every professional teacher. Null, 2011 as cited in Syarief (2017) said that teachers need to be knowledgeable about curriculum and the process by which curricula may be developed. When teachers consider the curriculum issues there are raised up fundamental questions about why, what, how and when to teach? Why do we teach in the first place? What do we expect out of the activity called teaching? After these general questions, other many curriculum directed questions are arising for the teachers and the curriculum developers such as: What knowledge is of most useful to the learners? What activities are most effective in enabling learners to acquire this knowledge (information, facts, skills, values, attitude, etc.)? What is the most appropriate way to organize these activities? How do I know if learners have acquired this knowledge?

The process of curriculum development is essential for successfully achieving educational goals for students. The term or the concept 'curriculum development' provides itself to different interpretations and is not easy to capture in one description or process. It is a complex but dynamic process which tends to lead to many interpretations and perspectives. Normally a curriculum is developed by designers at various levels (governmental or departmental) and implemented by practitioners at the other levels, by teacher in schools (Mostert, 1986 'b' as cited in Carl, 2009).

Curriculum development is an umbrella concept for the process which is

characterized by the presence of phases such as curriculum design, dissemination, implementation and evaluation. It is ongoing and dynamic process which involves a variety of persons and role players (Carl, 2009). NCF (2019) has defined curriculum development as the process of planning learning opportunities intended to bring about certain desired changes in pupils, and the assessment of the extent to which these changes have taken place. NCF emphasizes the importance of professional development of teachers with a focus on curriculum development and implementation in order to ensure that teachers understand the curriculum content and the process involved in supporting curriculum to make sound decisions about what is important for students to learn. "Teachers play fundamental roles in the application of curriculum process in their classrooms. Whether teachers are directly responsible for curriculum development or whether they interpret, implement, modify existing curriculum documents, they require a sound, substantive understanding of how it may affect them and their students" (Bishop, 1989 as cited in Print, 2020, p. 3). Clearly, teachers participate in multiplicity of curriculum activities at classroom level. These are the very substance of their daily teaching tasks and include such activities as selection of specific content, selection of teaching strategies, use instructional material and so forth. As implementers, teachers' role is to apply curriculum developed elsewhere and has a minimum responsibility and involvement in the curriculum development phase of the curriculum process (Print, 2020, pp. 16-17).

“Teachers may undertake the vital role of curriculum researcher as teachers become involved with school-level curriculum decision making, they require a sound understanding of curriculum concepts and processes” (Kelly, 2009, p. 118). Planning, design and development in curriculum are closely related terms. Once a curriculum has been conceptualized, through the process of curriculum planning and incorporating a curriculum design, it may then be developed, usually to become a written document and finally to be implemented and evaluated. All this curriculum process become successful and applicable whenever a teacher gets directly involved in the whole process (Wiles, 2009).

In Nepal, the Education Act and Regulations 8th amendment (2004) has entrusted the Curriculum development center [CDC] for the development of curriculum for the school level. So, the center plays a vital role for curriculum development, updating, revision and improvement and has developed a mechanism for collecting information and feedback on curriculum from its users (students and teachers) and other stakeholders. One of the most important elements in a successful school teaching program is the existence of a well-articulated curriculum. Definitely, a teacher is the primary audience of the curriculum development. Only professional and efficient teachers can serve the curriculum development process because they are the ones who have authentic knowledge on what students have already learned and what is required to prepare for the upper levels (Joshi, n. d). Therefore, curriculum

articulation becomes smooth if the teachers are involved in the curriculum development process.

Furthermore, their engagement in the curriculum development process helps to develop their ownership and commitment for the effective implementation of curriculum. Traditional view of curriculum implies that curriculum is developed by one set of people, implemented by another and received by yet another. This is the way of perceiving curriculum which is sometimes described as naturally occurring "thing" (Grundy, 1987; Maphosa & Mutoppa, 2012). Curriculum is also viewed as an activity or plan of action (Stenhouse, 1975; Su, 2012). But "curriculum is in the mind of the curriculum transmitter, and can only be learned from the words and actions of such a mind" (Sharpes, 2013, p.19). What is the situation of curriculum development in Nepal in terms of ‘developer’, ‘implementer’ dichotomy? How teachers are talking and fulfilling their roles in curriculum development? There are some important questions relating to the process of curriculum development in Nepal and the participation of teachers in it.

Taba (1962), as cited in Ornstein and Hunkins, (2016) said that the teachers should participate in developing curriculum. She felt that the administrative model was really in wrong order. Curriculum should be designed by the user of the program that is classroom teacher. Curriculum perceived in this light requires active teacher participation in its making. In other words, a teacher is the most important person in designing and improving the curriculum. Sharpes (2013) explains that "curriculum is

what the teacher does and what the teacher knows, and who the teacher is, the teacher's behavior, knowledge and personality" (p. 11). Since teachers are the critical agents for bringing changes into their classrooms, the teachers themselves should be the major focus of analysis and source of evidence regarding the introduction of curriculum development (Doyle & Ponder, 1977 as cited in Anthony, 2008).

Statement of the Problem

After analyzing several related documents this is come to know that there are several barriers and problems to make curriculum development process participatory. NCF (2019) has mentioned that;

Curriculum development process is required to be highly participatory such that curriculum experts are teamed up with parents, teachers, gender experts, experts of child-centered teaching and learning, and representative ethnic minorities, Dalits, and people with disabilities so that curriculum becomes non-discriminatory and based upon principles of social inclusion and equity (p. 8).

Without seriously considering the participants' voices, this study could not have provided detailed and deep understanding about the curriculum concept, curriculum development process and teachers' participation in it. So, it was imperative to understand and appreciate the voices of teachers. Since teachers are the critical agents for bringing changes into their classrooms, the teachers themselves

should be the major focus of analysis and source of evidence regarding the introduction of curriculum development (Doyle & Ponder, 1977).

Certain key questions such as the following arise: How the teachers understand and explain the curriculum? What are teachers' perceptions in respect of their present role in curriculum development, or what should they be? To what extent are the voices of teachers who wish to become more involved taken in cognizance for ensuring their access and participation? If such opportunities do exist, what is the nature and scope of their participation? What is the present tendency regarding teacher's participation in terms of being recipients or partners in curriculum development process?

Purpose and Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to explore the teachers' perception of curriculum development process, their concept of curriculum itself and their ownership of the curriculum. Thus, this study aims to seek teachers' participation in existing curriculum development process of Nepal. Indeed, the following research questions were answered via this study:

1. How do teachers perceive the practice of curriculum development process in Nepal?
2. How do teachers participate in curriculum development process?

Literature Review

Creswell (2017) says that literature review relates a study to larger ongoing dialogue in the literature about a topic, filling in gaps and extending prior studies. Literature review can be accepted as the integrative summary of broad themes, theories, experiences, existing policies and practices in the research topic. Indeed, I had gone through the different sources to review related literature to finalize my topic of research, filling the gaps of knowledge and extending prior studies. They are books, journal articles, empirical studies, policy related documents, historical documents and theories related to curriculum development.

School Level Curriculum Development Process in Nepal

The concept of curriculum and the process of curriculum and textbook development have been changed in recent years. Curriculum is now viewed as a process and it includes intended, taught and learned curriculum. In this context, we need to capture the interactive, dynamic nature of the curriculum process where national education goals are established. Also, the curriculum development process needs to be changed so that many actors such as female and male teachers, other educators with recent teaching experience, curriculum experts, and members of the wider community become actively involved.

As indicated in the 'Curriculum and Textbook Development Guidelines' (2002), CDC draws from the following sources for the development of new curriculum:

- Recommendations given by education commissions formed at the national level.
- Suggestions provided by teachers.
- Suggestions and reactions obtained through workshops and interaction programs attended by teachers, guardians, social workers, and intellectuals.
- Suggestions received from various sectors established to develop human resources.
- Objectives, policies and programs determined for the purpose of updating curriculum on timely manner.
- Innovations, research and development outcomes and philosophy of education.
- Suggestions and advice received from different channels of communication.

According to (Ministry of Education [MOE], 2004), National Curriculum Council [NCC] chaired by the minister of education, approves all curriculums and guides the detailed development work of the CDC by setting operational and administrative policy. NCC forms technical committees when additional advice is required. Matters concerning the relevance of curricula drafted by CDC may be redrafted by such a technical committee if the NCC feels the need of additional advice. CDC is responsible for the maintenance, transmission and renewal of the school education curriculum.

The wide-ranging activities of the centre include developing, revising and disseminating textbooks and teacher's

support materials. A program of seminars and workshops supports these activities. CDC's development and monitoring work is carried out by curriculum subject units, advised by curriculum subject specialist committees. Subject unit covers languages, sciences and math, social studies, health and physical education. To support CDC's activities, various studies and surveys are conducted on curriculum related issues and problems. The activities of CDC give rise to a wide range of relationships with other institutions. The most important of these relationships is with teachers and student in schools who are the immediate end users of the centre's products (MOE, 2004).

CDC claim that it has developed a mechanism for collecting information and feedback on curriculum from its users (students and teachers) and other stakeholders such as parliamentarians, guardians, school management committees, members of district education committees, special needs groups and civil society. Furthermore, curriculum updating, revision and improvement also claimed to be done according to the feedback received from different types of stakeholders and through piloting of the curriculum (NCF, 2019).

The curriculum development process described in any the 8th amendment of education and education act 2004, appendix-7, rule 32 is followed the following steps.

1. In any subject area, a write-up subcommittee consisting of the Curriculum Officer of the CDC and

other subject experts first draft the curriculum.

2. The subcommittee then submits the draft curriculum to the Curriculum Textbook Subject Committee (CTSC) consisting of subject teachers, teacher educators, and university professors

for comprehensive review.

3. CTSC reviews the draft curriculum on the basis of objectives, content, curricular weighting, instructional materials, and assessment methods.
4. If deemed necessary, the CTSC makes necessary additions or deletions and if major revision is needed the CTSC sends it back to the subcommittee for redrafting or revising the draft curriculum.
5. In Nepal with deep study, detailed analysis of experts and curriculum officers, drafting and redrafting and revising curriculum was developed and improved.
6. The final draft is submitted to the national curriculum committee for approved.

After reviewing the curriculum development process in Nepal, I have come to know that the centre plays a vital role for curriculum development, update, revision and improvement and has developed a mechanism for collecting information and feedback on curriculum from its users (Students and teachers) and other stakeholders.

Teacher's Role in Curriculum Development Process

As we are saying teachers are the curriculum themselves. They do not need to implement the curriculum as they adapt from some agency. They can develop their own curriculum. Carl (2009) said that the direct participation of teachers in the curriculum process will ensure the levels of successes, they must therefore, demand their voices to be heard while developing curriculum. Teachers want to be partners in the process of curriculum development and not mere passengers or onlookers. Teachers' involvement, co-operation and their role is said to be crucial for consultation and receiving feedback before and during the design phase; while there will be greater participation during implementation and evaluation. Hence teacher is a core person whose responsibility in regard to curriculum development cannot be entirely ignored (Print, 2007).

After reviewing the teachers' role in curriculum development process, it is come to know that policy formulation, curriculum design and planning, curriculum construction, testing the materials and curriculum improvement, implementation, evaluation, and quality control are the major areas of curriculum practice in which the role of teacher may seems to be very crucial. Every nation has its own policy and practices of the role of teacher to participate in curriculum development. No one can distract the teacher from this process but the dimension may vary for nation to nation.

International Curriculum Development Practices

The nature of curriculum development may vary in accordance with the national philosophy, aims, goal and purpose of education. According to Ornstein and Hunkins (2016), the state sets the broad curriculum guidelines for what students should know and be able to do. School districts or schools generally select textbooks, adhering to state guidelines in the U.S. Within these guidelines, schools and even individual teachers are generally expected to determine content details and the pace of instruction so that it is suited to the characteristics of students.

Elementary schools do not generally assign students to specific teachers or classes based on their ability (U. S Department of Education, 2008). Hence in United State of America the main responsibility of curriculum development is on the teachers' shoulders because teachers know every student's pace of learning.

According to the Australian curriculum for the learning area (ACARA, 2012), process for developing the Australian curriculum has been involved broad engagement with, and discussion and feedback about, the shape and content of curriculum that involves four interrelated phases. Curriculum shaping includes key periods of consultation- open public consultation as well as targeted consultation with key stakeholders including teachers and schools, state and territory education authorities, parents and students, professional

associations, teacher unions, universities and industry and community groups.

China has adopted three level Curriculum development and management system.

National, State and School-based curriculum account for 80%, 15% and 5%, respectively in the whole national curriculum plan. Based on local condition, schools can develop their own curricula or implement the national curriculum creatively, such that students can have a wide range of choices in their studies. This was the first time that the central government announced that schools, on a national scale should design their own curricula to some extent. Teaching periods have also been guaranteed. These policies guaranteed some chances for schools, including their teachers, to participate in curriculum development (Education Committee of China, 1997 as cited in Law Hau- Fai & Nieveen, 2010).

The process of curriculum development in India lies between the two extremes of centralization and decentralization from time to time, the national government formulates the national policy on education [NPEs] which includes broad guidelines regarding content and process of education at different stages. These guidelines are further elaborated by the national council of educational research and training [NCERT]. Using the NPEs of 1968 and 1986, two curriculum initiatives have been launched by NCERT. The curriculum framework prepared at the central level provides a broad overview of the school curriculum, including general objectives, subject-wise objectives, suggested scheme of studies and

guidelines for the transaction of the curriculum and the evaluation of pupil outcomes. These detailed curricula, syllabi and instructional materials are developed at the national level.

NCERT has also develops the syllabi and instructional materials to be used in the schools run by central organizations. However, the states consider whether to adopt or adapt the NCERT syllabi and instructional materials. Thus, the NCERT curriculum framework is always a suggestion rather than prescriptive and it is not enforceable by law in the states. However, it is readily accepted by the states because of the NCERTs credibility and the participatory development approach it follows (NCERT, 2006).

By reviewing the above literature, it is come to know that different countries have different practices of curriculum development. United States gives priority to individual teacher participation to determine content details and the pace of instruction. Australia has the priority for shaping, writing, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and review of curriculum development process

Chinese policy guarantees their teachers participation in curriculum development process. India has more rigid policy for the teachers' participation in curriculum development. National curriculum framework binds the perimeters of teachers' involvement in curriculum development process. State should develop its curriculum by the active participation of teachers under

the curriculum guideline provide by central government. So, it seems to be the participatory approach of curriculum development.

Empirical Review

In this section I have tried to review some empirical review which are related to my topic of the study are as follows:

Maphosa and Mutopa (2012) conducted research in, "Teacher's awareness of their role in planning and implementing school-based curriculum innovation". Purpose of this study was determining teachers' awareness of their role in planning and implementing school-based curriculum innovation. A quantitative-cum- qualitative survey design was used. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 242 teachers. Interview were held purposeful sample of teachers who had responded to the questionnaire. This study found that teachers were generally aware of their role in planning and implementation of school-based curriculum but their understanding of their role was as limited as their understanding of the concept of curriculum. This study recommends the emphasis of teacher training to enhance teacher's knowledge of curriculum and their role in planning and implementing school-based curriculum development. Indeed, teacher must have the conception of curriculum to participate and enhance the quality of curriculum. Hence the awareness of teacher to the concept of curriculum may increases their participation in curriculum development.

Mosothwane (2012) did his study, " The role of senior secondary school mathematics teachers in the development of mathematics curriculum in Botswana". Purpose of this study was examines the role played by secondary school mathematics teachers in the development of mathematics curriculum. It was conducted using a sample of 60 senior secondary school mathematics teachers. The findings of this study suggested that the majority of senior secondary school teachers' play only a minor role in the development of the mathematics curriculum, but are active in the implementation and production stages. This study suggested that full participation of teacher in the development of the curriculum would help them to better implement the material because they would feel their own. Teachers use a variety of teaching methods and materials to promote effective learning. An effective curriculum would develop if teachers were encouraged to participate in the development process.

After reviewing the above empirical literatures, it seems that teacher and curriculum development practices have the inseparable relationship. Different scholars did their study in their own perspectives. Whatever the approach of study one thing that is common to all of them is that the teachers' participation in curriculum development process was widespread. Nature of participation may vary from school to national level and from inception of curriculum development to the revision and quality assurance of developed curriculum. Without teacher's participation, curriculum development process won't be success in any society and nation. So this

review makes me think about the gap in the tendency of this participation in our context and at this context a question is pertinent. How is curriculum practice going on with teacher's role and responsibility in our secondary education system?

Theoretical Review

Theory is a formal set of ideas that is intended to explain why something happens or exists and it is established to suggest application of practical value.

Habermas's Practical Interest

Habermas calls historical-hermeneutics, a way of interpreting the meaning system of people and cultures. Its goal is to achieve understanding by making explicit the patterns of consensus and reciprocity that make human interaction possible. The practical/hermeneutic interest refers to those aspects of knowledge and action which are concerned with attaining and extending understanding and consensus in inter-subjective relations so as to achieve community and mutuality. Historical-hermeneutic knowledge yields 'interpretation' and is structured into process of understanding (Zajda, 2010). It is premised on the view that reality is socially constructed. Knowledge is constituted in free communication between persons. Curriculum informed by a practical interest is regarded as a process through which pupil and teacher interact in order to construct meaning. Hebermas claims that the link between understanding and action is the hermeneutic concept of application. Hermeneutic knowledge is always mediated

through pre-understanding, which is derived from the interpreter's initial situation (Habermas, 1971 as cited in Zajda, 2010).

So the curricular process is subjective and is informed by practical interest. Hence practical interest gives emphasis to practice rather than the outcome or product. Meaning making is also the form of learning for the students and teachers as they interact with each other in their attempt to understand. Not only that it also states that teachers are not a mere implementer of a planned programme but act as decision makers themselves when they exercise their own practical judgment in their students' learning. In fact the teacher's role would also involve in all aspect of curriculum development. When the practical interest influences the curriculum practices, they may be facilitated by the teachers' pedagogical skills but may depend more on teachers exercising their judgment. Curriculum in practical interest is based on practical activity of the process of interaction between teachers and students.

Conceptual Framework

To give the right way and direction for my research work, I try to make my own conceptual framework

Figure: Conceptual Framework of the Study

After analyzing various literatures in relation to teachers' participation and curriculum development process, and relevant theories for my argument, I have developed a conceptual framework for this study. I have tried to outline the inter-link relationship between Habermas theory, my beliefs and philosophical lenses, phenomena under study and method and approaches that I adopted for this study here.

Methodology

This study derives from interpretive research paradigm, which is depended on qualitative information gathered during fieldworks carried out in schools of Chitwan district.

Narrative Inquiry

As Pinar (2012) said "Curriculum is the interdisciplinary study of educational experiences" (p.2). "Curriculum is experienced in situations and that people have experiences which are, by nature, made up of and surrounded by other people and the environment" (Connelly & Clandinin, 1988 as cited in Kitchen, Parker & Pushor, 2011, p. 7). Also "To understand curriculum, is to understand one's personal lived experiences, school experiences and outside of school experience that make up the core of education because teacher's knowledge is found and lived in their narratives of experiences and then is educative" (Kitchen, Parker & Pushor, 2011,

p. 7). So, I had listened and collected stories of teachers, taking their stories and translating them into my own narratives about the issues that concerned them. I understand story from their point of view and see the world from their perspective because my research topic is "Teachers' Participation in Curriculum Development Process".

Selection of the Research Participants

I seek to understand the meaning of phenomena from participants' perspective. Without active and appropriate participants, my study would not have reached a meaningful conclusion. Thus, it was really important for me to select participants who could provide rich information and relevant data to answer my research questions. Having this concept in mind, I selected my participants purposefully according to the nature of study and my research questions.

Data Collection Procedure

The use of multiple data collection methods contributed not only to trustworthiness and validity of interpretation, but also to the creation of thicker and richer description in the data (Glesne, 2011). In accordance with my research purpose, I collected data through interviews, observations, document analysis and informal conversations with participants.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data analysis and interpretation is a continuous process that begins as soon as data are received. Every research study

requires precise decision about how the analysis and interpretation of data will be done. In narrative analysis and interpretation of data, I adopted sequential process of description, analysis, and interpretation (Wolcott, 1994 as cited in Creswell, 2017). When I finished my field work, I managed and organized data by creating different files for different data. I have tried to organize very essential data from the textual data and field notes after the transcription of raw data. Then I read through these text data and made some margin notes from initial codes. I tried to make different stories and themes with the help of field note, key note and transcription of conversations and again wrote the stories based on narrative elements into a chronological sequence (Creswell, 2017).

Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is the degree to which the research is deemed valid or warranted, as dictated by all of those involved in the process and by those evaluating the process (Lauridsen, 2003). Lather (2002) identifies four techniques for establishing trustworthiness which are credibility, transferability via thick description, dependability and conformability via audit trail, and reflective journal. I used rigorous methods of data collection and data analysis to enhance the trustworthiness in my research. I followed as Glesne (2011) point out that the researcher must demonstrate prolonged engagement, persistent observation, triangulation, peer review, debriefing, negative case analysis, clarification of researcher bias, member

checks, rich, thick description, and external audits to establish the trustworthiness of the research. I tried to adopt these through the journey of my research. For this, I used different evidences, arguments, personal beliefs and my honesty. I also addressed multiple voices of my participants. I used different strategies like working in a natural setting, understanding the context, interacting with participants, capturing the multiple voices of participants, using reflective analysis and applying multiple layers of interpretation.

Ethical Consideration

Any research which is only duplicating existing research or which does not have a quality to contribute new knowledge to the existing knowledge can be seen as unethical. So being ethical is crucial in every stage of research work not only in data collection. Macmillan and Schumacher (2001) states, "Ethical guidelines include informed consent, deception, confidentiality, anonymity, harm, privacy and others" (p. 420). Ethical considerations were taken for this study, by ensuring, as far as possible, that respondent's anonymity was protected. I tried to follow ethical consideration during my research with strong honesty and I tried to build rapport and trust in my site. For this, I never forced them to answer my question according to my expectation and I also did not try to ask any questions about their personal life. Further, I did not compel my participants so that they were free to answer my questions. If they wanted privacy and confidentiality, I assured them how the data was to be used and stored securely. Participation was voluntary in this

research. So it was assured that they were free to withdraw from the research at any time if they faced any problem or discomfort.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The main purpose of this chapter is to bring out the perception of curriculum development process and experience of participation of teacher in this process. I have tried to explore the various concepts of curriculum development process from the teachers' perspective. Not only that I have also tried to discuss the practices of curriculum development process and experiences of teacher's participation on it.

Practices of Curriculum Development Process in Nepal

Different concepts of curriculum have emerged from both theoretical and practical perspectives. A common feature is that curriculum is central to the education process and includes the sum of teaching and learning activities provided by schools. How we see the curriculum and curriculum development process directly shapes and influences our practices. So, we need to think regularly about what underline our ideas, our reasoning and practice are never value free or neutral.

The development of curriculum, Stenhouse (1975 as cited in Kelly, 2004) regards as vital and states that individual teacher accepts a role in respect to the curriculum by modifying, adapting and developing it to suit the needs of individual pupils and a particular environment. Thus, it appears that

the participation of teachers in the curriculum development process is important. NCF (2019) has defined curriculum development as the process of planning learning opportunities intended to bring about certain desired changes in pupils, and the assessment of the extent to which these changes have taken place. NCF emphasizes the importance of professional development of teachers with a focus on curriculum development and implementation in order to ensure that teachers understand the curriculum content and the process involved in supporting curriculum to make sound decisions about what is important for students to learn. I have made separate sub themes on the perception of teacher' of practices of curriculum development process in Nepal.

Gap in Written and Implemented Process

In this part of analysis, I have tried to present the story of my respondent as a snipped conversation. This section is very helpful for me to present how the participants of this study understand and perceive the curriculum development practices in the Nepalese context.

Researcher [R]: How do you take your teaching experiences? What do your experiences say?

Respondent first [R₁]: Now, the teaching learning practice of school education is based on interest of private textbook and practice book writers which is totally out of curriculum prescribed by the government. The objectives and subject matters determined by curriculum are in one side and

textbook is in different edge. Teaching process has been directionless crossing the curriculum outline by including unnecessary questions in the name of different pretest and test question.

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Respondent second [R₂]: The courses to be taught are determined by curriculum development centre. Foreign resource materials are taken as sources by curriculum development centre. This is a cause of gap in written and implementation of curriculum development practices in Nepal.

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Respondent third [R₃]: Theoretically the course seems very good but the time has changed with changes in technology.

So our course doesn't succeed to meet the learning objectives practically. We deliberate subject matter from the top. I mean students acquire very little at the end of every academic year. Nothing remains in student's hand as well as in mind.

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R: How do you take the objective mentioned in curriculum? What do your experiences say?

R₁: I am assured that the objectives in curriculum are good. They are based on students' age and psychology but the subject matter is vague due to private textbook writers.

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R₂: Objectives mentioned in curriculum are not attained in the context of Nepal, although it thoroughly sounds relevant. Subjective achievement is only up to 50%, it won't cross 60% in S.L.C if we assume those

students who score 32% mark out of 100% teaching as passed. Curriculum has been proved a failure everywhere. Today, students are unsuccessful and of teachers, teaching institute and nation are unsuccessful as well. The main reason of this is either the failure of curriculum or curriculum objective. It is a matter of research.

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R₃: As I told earlier it is good but behavioral part is problematic. In my teaching experiences, I succeed to make many students pass out from the school but I haven't seen any student self dependent in their career.

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R: How far are the subject matters mentioned in curriculum relevant? **R₁:** The teaching learning activities for student would be convenient if we can construct suitable textbook based on curriculum outline by curriculum development centre. For this, government sensation is needed for private writer.

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R₂: Subject matter of curriculum is determined based on objective. Subject matters may not be relevant in spite of being relevant to objective.

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R₃: Of course the subject matter included in curriculum is relevant for each level but is not practical. My long experiences of teaching learning ensured this and I personally experienced this situation.

.....

R: How do you use curriculum textbook? Do you adjust some or use exactly as it comes from centre? How do you decide?

R₁: Textbook is not constructed/designed according to broader form of curriculum. Broader forms of curriculum are not obeyed while designing curriculum according to unit wise subject matter of textbook and while designing university lecture. Haphazard questions of upper level are included in particular grade level. Once the textbook is designed it is disseminated after its evaluation by experienced and interested teachers. As a result teaching learning activities would be fruitful.

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R₂: The curriculum that comes from centre is implemented making some adjustments. Some of the subject matters are put up-down during implementation. The implementation rests generally on the individual teacher though sometimes brief discussion sessions are organized at the resource centre level.

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R₃: I used as it according that's from centre but sometimes presentation of subject matter is reviewed at the end of intake.

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R: Do you know, which objective or subject matter functions or not at the local level?

R₁: Designing the local curriculum is based on the objective of skilled manpower. But in our context it is not fulfilled due to the lack of proper support of resources from the government side. We have trained teachers but do not have the economic sustainability to design and prescribe local curriculum. Talking about the national objective, whether they are functioning or not at the local level is very much doubtful question for me because we are producing many

failure students incapable of competing in job market.

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R₂: Sometimes teaching was carried out in some context according to our circumstances even though the particular subject matters are directed from centre. Specially, we used the skill oriented subject like pre-vocational education based on localism at that time. We equally studied the same regional subject matter which was used in local level.

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R₃: Of course -not, because our students don't have the ability to perform in daily life. For example in the case of mathematics we teach home arithmetic every year but the students could not check electricity bill or water bill.

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R: Do you have any experiences in relation to curriculum implementation and evaluation at local level? How are the other teachers constructing local curriculum?

R₁: I haven't got any opportunity to participate in local curriculum design, development and implementation till now. Talking about national perspective, I have very less experiences of textbook writing and curriculum analyzing and rest of it. I am not able to say much more about this process.

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R₂: I haven't participated directly in the works to design local or national curriculum. Many friends have tried to work there while working under this training centre but failed to get complete achievement. Friends in some districts talk to design local

curriculum but government hasn't helped with means or resource or there isn't such management to make curriculum for local level. For this, required resources and material are not provided.

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R₃: I don't have such experiences of participating in curriculum conceptualization, design, development locally or nationally. I just have experienced its implementation and evaluation. I have not got any chance to discuss with my friend about this matter and I haven't participated locally or nationally. So I am not able to say anything about this.

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When analyzing above snipped story of participants regarding the understanding and perception about curriculum development, it seems that they understood curriculum development to be having a broad area. They tried to link it to the work of text formation of educational goals and objectives, textbook writing, achievement of intended objectives, student evaluation etc. Obviously it is related to curriculum development. At first we conceptualize a curriculum then we design, develop and manage it properly with the inclusion of need and interest of learner. Then we can see it through other perspective like global perspective. Whatever is the theoretical aspect, it seems that my respondents have conceptualized and understood that the curriculum development practice and process of Nepal, there is a gap between written and implementation process. They argue that most of the works in curriculum

process need to be performed by local teachers who are directly involved in its implementation. They believed and said that mismatch occurs in process of curriculum development.

Whatever we know and identify through our everyday experiences is not incorporated by the person who has participated in the work of curriculum design. And whatever they think and design, we can't achieve perfectly. It is because of the diverse culture and capability of learners in the field of implementation of written curricula. As Grundy (1987 as cited in Orestein & Hunkins, 2016) explains the concept of Habermas, the role of teacher is to facilitate students to make their own meanings and to have their own learning experiences and a teacher is the developer and initiator of curriculum change/development. Nepalese curriculum development practice seems to be gapping in written and implementation when we see the perspectives of NCF. It has explained the decentralization of curriculum development and my respondents have said that there is mismatch between policy and practice.

This gapping may be due to the effect of bureaucratization because from literature related to curriculum development shows that authority is provided to CDC for the process of curriculum development and monitoring by ministry of education. Even the teacher role is not completely neglected but this process is in the handful member of the sector of if we see the process development of curriculum in Nepal provision made by ministry of education. NCF (2019) explained are adopting the

process model of curriculum development but the local level teacher explored it isn't in practice. They said central level of textbook and curriculum development committee borrowed different members from other field rather than maximization of classroom teacher.

Centrally Dominated Curriculum Development Practice

With teaching experience of more than thirty years, and other professional experiences including writing of textbooks, respondent Sanjaya describes the curriculum development process and practice of Nepal as;

Curriculum development policy of our country is somehow good because it is revised in every five years. Curriculum is developed in various steps from lower to upper level based on time, innovation of knowledge and influences of information technology in knowledge development. On the basis of learners' identification of problem, need, relevancy, utility, and importance and so on curriculum is developed. For that different task like curriculum pattern construction (design), writing, implementation, evaluation and revision are applied. Theoretically speaking, curriculum is constructed with the consent of school resource centre to district, zone, and development region to the national level with the participation of teachers. Curriculum is designed and written with the broad discussion, conducting national seminar but it isn't practical.

From the above story we can say that Sanjaya has knowledge about curriculum development concept and process. He has clearly described the process of curriculum development in Nepal. He has clear concept about this; it's a thing that need to be explored and I have tried to explore this concept from his perspective. He said that he had a chance to participate in textbook writing and revision as he received the major work of curriculum development and deliberation in school level. His understanding is;

Teacher bears the problem in teaching profession. Any Ph. D. holder expert can't understand the level wise problem and tendency if he /she do not teach in the level wise grade. For that more experienced teachers are needed because only qualified ones can't design the curriculum and teach. This is not adopted in our country. Only the teachers who have knowledge about the child's mental capacity, subject matter relevancy, scope etc can design and teach the curriculum accordingly. Curriculum and textbook are not same and are incomplete in the lack of teachers' participation. Teachers' participation in curriculum development is very important because they experience how to simplify the curriculum, how to divide and how to teach. No one has understood about society, social needs, students and their needs, capacity, interest etc as a teacher. So first observe potentiality and capability of the child while developing curriculum not the reverse of it.

After analyzing above information, there is a mismatch between policy of curriculum development and its actual practices. My respondent has knowledge of curriculum development process; theoretically and practically in the context of Nepal. He had the experiences of curriculum implementation, textbook writing and revision. He said that he bears several problems in the field of teaching learning from several years of experiences. He is willing to participate in other processes of curriculum development to share the problem of education and everyday curriculum practices in classroom, subject matter relevancy and needs of Nepali students. NCF (2019) has mentioned that;

Curriculum development process is required to be highly participatory such that curriculum experts are teamed up with parents, teachers, gender experts, experts of child-centered teaching and learning, and representative ethnic minorities, dalits and people with disabilities so that curriculum becomes non-discriminatory and based upon principles of social inclusion and equity (p. 8).

The process of curriculum development in Nepal seems participatory, inclusive and equitable in policy. Regarding the scenario of practices in real manner, my respondent remembered that he had not got such opportunity to participate in central level of curriculum and textbook writing committee.

However he said that he got chance of textbook writing and revising from Chitwan district for some chapters. In the personal

communication of our regular meeting he said;

People say curriculum development process is inclusive, participatory; I don't care about it because in more than thirty years period of my teaching life no one called me to participate in the process of curriculum design and development. I got few opportunities to participate in textbook writing and revision workshop after putting several strong demands. In Chitwan, several experienced and trained teachers are teaching different subjects for long time. If you can ask them, whether they had got any chances to participate in any processes other than implementation of curriculum, no one answers positively. It's a language game or a written document prepared sitting in air conditioned room of any hotel in Kathmandu. (From my field note)

When I discussed about the teachers' participation in curriculum development process one of the member of CDC had said that teachers were participate in design, development, implementation and revision of the curriculum from each district, zone and regional level. They have given different responsibilities from different stage of curriculum development. We don't think that they have only the responsibility of implementation and evaluation of curriculum in the process of curriculum development. Our policy has declared that we have to adopt the integrated and process model of curriculum development (NCF, 2019).

After listening to the respondent's feeling I have come to know that he is willing to participate in national curriculum committee and textbook writing but he has not got any opportunity. I don't think that did not get chance to participate in curriculum development, design and so on. He told me that he had got many chances to participate in different meetings, seminars and workshop related to curriculum development, implementation, revision, textbook writing at district and regional level. He is trying to say that we are moving towards the centrally dominated curriculum development process rather than adopting curriculum as process following the Stenhouse's model of curriculum development as declared by our curriculum policy. The evidences that I found from my respondents gives the glimpse of centralized culture of curriculum practices. In most of the countries, curriculum development is generally centralized, but at the implementation level there is varying degree of autonomy of local authorities, schools and teachers (NIER, 1999). So after reviewing the above information we can say that our curriculum development practices are in traditional mode till now. It indicates that our policy tries to direct us towards progressive curriculum and practices and they lead us towards technical rationality.

When we view curriculum as practice then each school would be responsible and accountable for the development and evaluation of their own educational policies and practices. There would be neither a centralized curriculum nor the centralized examination system because power resides

with school and not the policymakers and other (Habermas, 1972 as cited in Kelly, 2004). So we can predict that centralized educational practice could not be able to include the teachers from diverse groups and cultures from the local communities. By viewing respondents' opinions we can say that our system of curriculum practices is not able to incorporate the local teachers in overall process of curriculum development.

Teachers felt that our curriculum development practice becomes centrally dominated because in review of literature related with others country they were provided more authority and responsibility to the local level but in our situation it is seen just opposite of others. Also teachers said instead of knowing local resources, needs and aspiration foreign experts or Nepalese experts from the different university was used to planning and designing curriculum centrally. Local teachers have more responsibility with in implementation and evaluation of centrally prescribed curriculum all over the country because of centrally governance system and its impact on education.

Decentralization of Curriculum Development Practice: Inclusive and Participatory

Some participants believe that decentralization of curriculum making is more inclusive and participatory, so that it would be able to reflect the local knowledge and needs of learners. Knowledge economy is the priority of 21st century; therefore exploration of local knowledge can

contribute global knowledge and thereby help in making connection of local knowledge with global knowledge. Some participants also believe that curriculum become fruitful if it made skill based so that our students can have a place in international job market. In this connection Narayan said; *Teachers are said to participate only in policy not in practice. Curriculum development has been centralized only in capital city or in main city centre. We stayed in old system; curriculum development process hasn't been keeping pace with the world in this 21st century. Now our students are spreading all over the world to study where they are getting problem of marks equivalence and we could develop in such a way that it is accepted internationally. I have not experienced any functions, discussions or seminars related to curriculum development till now in Chitwan district. I would have participated if that had been done. Teacher is said to play with the curriculum as s/he uses the curriculum daily. Teachers keep all the information about student's interests, wants, needs, national condition etc. because they stay in local environment, culture and society. So teacher's participation to curriculum development should be enlarged.*

Narayan perceived that in the process of curriculum development, teachers are considered as knowledge representatives of learners and school milieu. Teachers are assisted by representatives of all bodies of knowledge, especially representatives of subject matter and the curriculum process. In the process of curriculum development, teachers' role may be compared to the role of musicians who perform the creation of

composers. A musician may make his own interpretations of a composition (Ben-Peretz, 1980; Srivastava & Kumari, 2005). Likewise, in the curricular approach, teachers were perceived as originator of the curriculum, composer of their own music. Their knowledge, attitude, concerns, and needs were the starting point of the curricular process. Teacher's expertise about classroom reality was considered to be crucial for discerning practical problem while constructing curriculum.

Teachers have intimate knowledge of learners, classrooms and school milieu. This knowledge allows teachers to point out weaknesses, shortcomings and conditions which should and can be placed. The perceptions of teachers are significant and crucial for curriculum development in practical manner. So it is considered that teachers are being assigned a primary role in curriculum development process. When I interviewed my respondent Krishna and asked have you got any chance to participate in curriculum development and design, he answered;

I haven't got any opportunity in curriculum design (arrangement of curriculum elements) and development. It is start from setting educational goal or policy design and end up in evaluation and revision. If the responsibilities of policy making and curriculum designing are provided to teacher then curriculum becomes practicable. Students' school dropout is the result of teachers' non participation. Teacher need to familiar with the things he uses. Teacher's experiences,

expertise need to be brought in curriculum so that it would be practical and behavioral to students.

Curriculum need to be based on nation's reality and should be relevant with change of time and applicable for student's adult behavior. Now the curriculum matter has come mechanically but it should go behaviorally. It has only been theoretical concept but is not effective from the perspective of student's skill development.

Krishna understands that curriculum development process proceeds from the formation of educational goal and ends at revision of curricular material or the design to revision of curriculum. He believes that curriculum is implemented effectively only if teacher participation is ensured from the design to revision of the curriculum. Teacher is the only person who directly intimately knows learners, classroom and school milieu. To make the child's friendly curriculum direct participation of teacher in curricular process is crucial. Teachers read every page of student and understand what subject matter is best suited, in which level and in which social milieu. It is known to those teachers who are directly involved in teaching learning process. He also understands that if the teacher participation in the curriculum development process becomes unsatisfactory then the problem of teacher's dropout from job and student drop out from classroom arises.

Krishna emphasized that teacher's experiences and expertise are crucial for the development of curriculum as stated in Stenhouse's process inquiry model of

curriculum development. Process inquiry model allows teachers to become artists rather than technician giving emphasis to a curriculum decision making and the curriculum development is the province of the local school (Mckernan, 2013). Also, Habermas claimed in his practical interest that curriculum design is regarded as a process through which student and teacher interact in order to construct new knowledge. So there is an alignment between Habermas' Practical interests of curriculum development and Stenhouse's process inquiry model of curriculum development. Both have a common ground that curriculum is not a means-ends by which educational outcomes will be produced through the action of a teacher upon a group of objectified pupils developed centrally as banking concepts as said by Frere (1970). Analyzing the perspective of respondents and from the review of related literature it is noticed that decentralization is one of the ways to incorporate the maximum teachers in the process of curriculum practices.

Hence by observing my respondents' understanding about the practices of curriculum development process, it is seen that they all are aware theoretically and practically on the process and practices of curriculum development in Nepal. They develop their own personal perception on the practices of curriculum development and design. They have a common view that the education system of any country in the world becomes worthless without teachers' participation in the whole curricular practices. Curriculum is developed for learners and teacher is that person who

intimately peruses the child's each and every behavioral activities. Teachers told that decentralization in curriculum development becomes more inclusive and participatory because they felt problem and barriers to implement and evaluation. Literature that I reviewed also shows the centralized system of curriculum development process. Our history of curriculum starts from spiritual scriptures to the current written document which was controlled in this or that way from the power coercive approach. The pipeline approach of our education system influenced our education system even if formal education starts from our modern age starts from the rise of democracy in Nepal. Different educational commission recommended different structure of curriculum and its development process but one thing remain unchanged that is the cultural hegemony to see local teacher as mere implementers rather than partner of development of central committee. Indeed teachers are demanded decentralization in curriculum development process now for inclusive and participatory.

Teachers' Participation in Curriculum Development

Talking in a broad sense, the curriculum development process includes the design, development, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and revision of curriculum. However, while examining the curriculum development process more precisely it becomes clear that each phase may itself comprise several varied but interrelated activities. In the design phase, curriculum is conceptualized and attention is paid to the

arrangement of the varied components, focusing on philosophical underpinnings, goals, objectives, subject matter, learning experiences and evaluation; all established in consultation with stakeholders. Then the curriculum is developed through planning, construction and logical step-by-step procedures are used to produce written document which include vision statements, goals, standards, performance benchmarks, learning activities and instructional activities, interdisciplinary connections and other integration activities that guide the curriculum implementation.

In the implementation phase, all the stakeholders become part of the process by making their contribution to operationalize the curriculum as designed and developed. Especially, classroom teachers have a crucial role in this phase of curriculum development process. Monitoring, as a part of the implementation process, verify the classroom practices consistent with the established goals and objectives of the curriculum. Evaluation process determines the effectiveness of curriculum design and its implementation as they relate to the child. Finally, curriculum review guides appropriate adjustment to the curriculum documents. In the section of literature review of this research, different literatures have shown that the teachers' participation in each and every phase of curriculum development process is crucial and has a significant role on it.

Inclusion on Teacher Participation

Here I have tried to present the teachers' understanding and dimension of their participation in curriculum development via the snippet story picking up their lived experiences.

R: *You have said that you couldn't participate in curriculum construction. Why did it happen? Can you share some story?*

R₁: *I don't have any comment on participation in curriculum construction but less time may be available for textbook reformation. At that time we can give the suggestion for future outline of textbook and some exchange in curriculum. For that the assurance of enough time is necessary for coming textbook reformation but as I know curriculum development centre's subject related personnel modified and replaced the experience teachers in later reformation, which was not suitable.*

.....

R₂: *Ironsmitths make sickle using their experience and skill by asking the user about the type while designing it. In spite of the difficulties or hardships during the process then design keeping users' psychology in mind as much as possible. Curriculum should be used by the teacher. They know how much effective has it been. What to do for betterment? The matters can be suitable if the teachers participate while designing, changing and modifying the curriculum. Most of the fellow teachers comment on curriculum while working as trainers in training centers. It would*

be better through teacher participation. It is due to the lack of effective mechanism for teacher participation.

.....
R₃: *In one hand our mechanism is not as good as it is written in policy document and so it couldn't ensure maximum teacher participation. I have not paid attention to the formal process of curriculum construction but focused on curriculum implementation.*

.....
R: *You have said that the teachers from out of valley have not participated. Why it would be you share your experiences?*

R₁: *It was the first time, during the curriculum reformation of grade 9 and 10 compulsory math in 2060 B. S. when the experienced teachers were brought from out of valley for the first time. Before this, we reformed the curriculum three four times calling famous, experienced teachers inside the Kathmandu valley but the problem remained where it was. Next time selection was done in seminar based report but curriculum development centre provided the opportunity to the inexperienced persons from the valley again.*

.....
R₂: *The question you put woke me up. The teacher from out of the valley like Chitwan, Makawanpur, and Dhading were not to be actively participating.*

.....
R₃: *I never participate in any programme held in curriculum development centre and that's why I don't have any experiences about the central level activities. As to say about*

my participation in local level, I haven't experiences that type of curricular activities instead of teaching.

.....
After analyzing above conversation of expression of teacher' participation in curriculum development process in Nepalese context, I reached to the conclusion that it is necessary to include teachers from varied geography, cultural group and curriculum should provide information about varied people, learners and school contexts (Stenhouse 1975, as cited Kelly, 2004). Respondents told that teachers from outside the capital city have not got any chance to participate in curriculum development though they are experienced and qualified to develop and implement the curriculum. Above data also shows that local curriculum development practices are not practicable despite what policy document said about the provision of local curriculum development. I reviewed different scenarios of international curriculum development practices and they give the clear picture of maximum participation of teachers in initiation of curriculum development. It shows not only the higher teacher participation in curriculum practices but also the higher educational achievement in these nations. National Institute of Educational Research [NIER] (1999) said that where diversities exist in community or society there it is necessary to involve local community in the curriculum development to promote unity of diversities. So in our context also diversity exists in various dimensions like ethnicity, cultural, linguistic and geographical. This indicates that we are also need to promote and involve the local teachers in the

initiation of curriculum development. Respondents that they have need inclusive curriculum development practices and here is no systematic input of teachers on policy development, training and curriculum review. Involvement of wide range of agencies and stakeholders is regarded as important factor to develop effective curriculum. NIER (1999) said that although final decisions are generally made at government level in most of the countries but stakeholders are consulted before and during the development process, mostly the classroom teachers. Indeed this information directs us to the future scene by showing the picture of past.

Teacher as a mere Implementer rather than Developer of Curriculum

Teachers' experiences and expertise are beneficial to each and every phases of curriculum development process; so is their participation in this process. About the participation in this process respondent Sanjaya said;

Teachers' participation in curriculum development process is essential in each step; not only in policy paper. Practically, it is limited only in the paper. The teachers from outside of Kathmandu valley have little or no opportunity in policy design, goal determination, draft construction, curriculum writing etc. Teacher's role is limited only in the text book writing, revising, curriculum implementation, evaluation etc. though they are also the part of different form of curriculum development process. Now, the

government should bring the new policy as to address the time's need which will ensure the teacher involvement in every phase of curriculum development process among the various community and places so that curriculum will be behavioral, internationally accepted based on nation's reality. Teacher's participation in every step of curriculum development process should be fixed which isn't done up to now in the nation.

Sanjaya discussed about the trends of curriculum development process on the basis of his lived experience. He said that very teachers were participated only in implementation and evaluation process from outside of valley. Teachers were involved in the phase of development from capital city. Sanjaya didn't know up to now that teachers are involved in design, revision and monitoring phase. He has to say that government should bring such a policy for curriculum development process so that teacher's participation in every phase will be ensured. He said;

It's all valley centered. I think the teachers from out of valley don't have any such type of opportunity in realistic manner. You have to follow baggy curriculum framework out of valley. I have doubt about the teachers who participate in design, constructions of the curriculum are really a teacher or not. Teacher from out of valley have not participated, they have not been asked and discussed while developing curriculum.

Teachers' participation in curriculum design and development activity is assumed crucial by many authors. Carl (2009) noted that the teacher must not be mere implementers but development agent who is able to develop, apply, and evaluate the relevant curriculum dynamically and creatively. Theoretically it is proved that teacher has such capability and expertise for the design and development of curriculum rather than as mere implementers. They have the ability required for development, implementation, evaluation and revision of dynamic and creative curriculum relevant to the learner's needs and aspirations. In the regular meeting and discussion with Sanjaya he told me;

I have not got any experiences of participation on overall process of curriculum development. I had experience of writing textbook and its revising it once. Being a classroom teacher responsibility of curriculum implementation and evaluation is obvious and I collected several experiences but I have not had any opportunity to explore these experiences of my teaching life in the task of designing the curriculum framework. I bear several problems in my teaching life related with learning experiences and so on. Teachers' participation is crucial and essential because teachers can and only understand the learners' needs, aspiration, capacity and interest. Teacher and student are living in the same society and culture so that teachers are able to diagnose ever aspects of learners. (From my personal field note)

From the Sanjaya's thought and belief, I have come to know that he had lot of experiences in teaching learning activities

and work of textbook writing. Curriculum needs to be constructed after analyzing the child's capacity, needs and interest and should not be vice-versa. So teachers' participation in curriculum development process seems to be crucial and another respondent Krishna has the similar types of understanding, perception and sorrow. He said;

I haven't got any opportunity to take part in policy making, curriculum design and writing although being a teacher I got the opportunity to participate variously in curriculum implementation, evaluation and revision. Truly, in every steps of curriculum development, if the curriculum development centre took idea, advice, suggestion of teachers than this would be better. Curriculum does not have any meaning and worth in real sense if it is developed without incorporating their experiences. Teacher study every aspects of student and co-ordinate with them. Teacher is a researcher of students and their society. I got a chance to participate in discussion of national curriculum framework and revision of curriculum once held in Kathmandu.

Krishan has perceived that teacher's idea, advice, and suggestion are beneficial to every steps of curriculum development. For that teachers' participation in every step would be better. He did not have any chance to participate in the phases of curriculum design, development except for being involved in some discussion program. Like other teachers, he had chance to

involve in implementation and evaluation phase only. Wiles and Bondi (2002) said that an emphasis should be given to the persons who should involve in curriculum designing and planning in general and the teachers in particular. But according to Krishna, in Nepalese context of curriculum development the teachers' participation in designing and planning phase was lacking. Emphasizing the importance of the participation of stakeholders in policy formulation Marsh (2009) said that proposals for curriculum reform can come from various sources; teachers, teacher unions, policy makers, academicians, politicians, media and pressure groups.

But Narayan understands that the politically oriented works could hamper teachers' participation in the curriculum development process and he couldn't have any chances to take part in curriculum design and development though he participated in implementation and evaluation process being a classroom teacher. He said in his interview;

I haven't got any opportunity to participate in curriculum development up to now. Opportunities may come only to those special teachers, who are in district centre, close teacher and relatives. I don't know the reality, but it seems that curriculum development process and its participation is centralized in reality.

Narayan perceived that teachers' participation in the curriculum development process of Nepal remains only in policy and document. He thinks that these activities

only remain in centre. He did not have any such opportunities though he passed several years of his teaching life in Chitwan. When I went through observing several documents of district education office of Chitwan and discussed with the staff members, I couldn't find any official records and evidences that were related to teachers' participation in curriculum design, development and revision. In Chitwan no such formal program, seminar and workshops were conducted. NIER (1999) explains that in some countries like Australia there are varying possibilities for local authorities, schools and teachers to influence curriculum development at the implementation level and such countries teachers develop their own content within centrally developed curriculum frameworks.

Regarding people's participation Carl (2009) wrote that, relevant curricula is, however, not only assured on the broad front but also through curriculum actions of those who are involved at other levels and in other fields (school, classroom). All persons involved in these processes from the classroom up to the national level should have a responsibility for relevant curriculum development. A curriculum should be grounded in practice. It is an attempt to describe the work observed in classrooms that it is adequately communicated to teachers and others (Stenhouse, 1975 as cited in Kelly, 2004). He conceptualizes the relationship between the learners, the teacher and the subject matter, placing the teachers right at the heart of the curriculum development process.

Reviewing the responses from all the respondents it is understood that their engagement is mainly limited to implementing, monitoring and evaluating curriculum; they do not have more role in the development process. Stenhouse's placed the teacher right in the centre of curriculum development process. Also Glanz and Horenstein (2000) stated that teacher explores student reactions and interactions with learning experiences and uses this information to design the curriculum in a way that is responsive to their needs. The development of curriculum must be responsive to cultural pluralism and individual uniqueness. Indeed teachers' participation is crucial to bring the culture and uniqueness of child at the process of curriculum development.

I reviewed different books, article, and research reports. Not only that I went through the education act of Nepal; all documents stated that teachers' participation in the process of curriculum development process is essential but when seen in reality it was not practiced by Nepalese curriculum development process. I selected my respondents very carefully so that I could succeed to select the participants having a lot of experiences in the field of education especially in teaching. But when I studied them very intimately then I realized that they had very limited opportunity to get involved in curriculum design, development and revision. However they had the opportunity to implement the intended curriculum and evaluate students' targeted performance.

In India, implementing curriculum is prescribed some degree of local interpretation. The general trends are toward the setting of national guideline with a certain degree of flexibility for interpretation at the local level (NCERT, 2006). A curriculum, no matter how good, will simply remain a curriculum on paper if it is not implemented properly. Teachers in schools are the key to implement of that curriculum. Teachers play a very important role in delivering the curriculum. Resistance sometimes exists because of the lack of their involvement in planning and designing, training and orientation prior to implementation of the curriculum. Indeed the participation of teacher is crucial for the initiation to the implementation of curriculum development. But the findings of this research show that teachers are the mere implementers of curriculum rather than developers.

This type of situation gives the picture of content-based model or objective model of curriculum development as we analyze above data in theoretical perspective. It means that we are following traditional approach of curriculum development. It's a ruled based technical rationality of curriculum development not a practical and humanistic approach of curriculum as said by Habermas' practical interest and Stenhouse' process inquiry model of curriculum development.

Combining Different Perspectives of Curriculum Development Process

Here in this section I have tried to triangulate different views about teachers' perception about curriculum development and their experiences of participation with different types of information found from literature and the field of study. Then I have tried to interpret it from the different perspective to make the appropriate meaning which makes this study more valid and trustable. No one can neglect the role of teacher in the curriculum development work but the dimension of participation is problematic for this work. Orestein and Hunkins (2016) said that teacher's ability to primary ingredient of teaching and learning is the local site (Goodlad, 1998 as cited in Lunenburg, 2011).

predict what is to be taught, in what order, in what way and by whom and their own instructional experiences of content is sufficient to engage in curriculum development work. Different philosophies and schools of thought of curriculum and its development have varied ideas and assigned varied role for teachers. Each and every theory and model has placed the central role for teacher in either ways. The key unit for the initiation of educational innovation, change in the individual school, and the chief decision makers in effectuating a curriculum plan are the school principal, teachers, students, parents and local community. Thus the

is the local site (Goodlad, 1998 as cited in Lunenburg, 2011).

Found From	Curriculum Development Process
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<p>Literature</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I found from empirical review is that ignoring teacher's voice in the curriculum development; the outcomes of curriculum may in fact be limited. So their participation is needed from inception to the production of actual materials. • I found greater participation of teachers in curriculum development locally or nationally from the international perspectives. Teacher is the responsible person of curriculum development because teacher knows every student's pace of learning. Teachers are expected to determine content details and pace of instruction because teacher's idea and role have greater position than those of others for curriculum development. • I found from literature review that teacher's role in curriculum development process is in policy formulation, design, development, implementation, evaluation, review and improvement. • Teacher's participation in policy formulation contributes to add to teacher's knowledge, skills and experiences and to enrich the policy. • Teacher's participation in curriculum design contributes to articulation, continuity, balance, situation analysis, formulation of goals, and selection of content or learning experiences. • Teacher's participation in curriculum development, implementation, evaluation, review and improvement gives the clear picture of curriculum, quality of curricular materials and the quality of education as well. • Historically Nepal follows the top-down approach of curriculum. Curriculum is viewed as taken for granted. • In current Nepalese curriculum development practice, curriculum is viewed as a process; emphasis is given to classroom teachers but the mechanism tries to control the whole process in practice.
<p>Theory</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical interest views curriculum as a process. Teachers are not mere implementers of a planned learning activity; they are the decision makers themselves in their classroom and for the learners. • Practical interest give emphasis on active participation of teacher in curriculum development. Curriculum is not successful without incorporating teacher's knowledge, skills and experiences and also without learner's needs and aspiration.
<p>Field Data</p>	<p>Teacher's Perception on Practices of Curriculum Development</p>

	Gap in Written and Implemented Process
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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Role of teacher as instructor of teaching textbook. |
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- | | |
|--|---|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• CDC doesn't follow the curriculum development policy; curriculum is prepared by collecting foreign curriculum practices.• Curriculum is not skill oriented it's just a collection of subject matter.• Local curriculum development is just for formality, not found in real practice.• Teachers from locality don't have any opportunities to participate in curriculum development process. They are only involved in teaching prescribed curriculum. |
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	Centrally Dominated Curriculum Development Practice
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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• According to policy provision curriculum is a process but it is not practiced. It seems that curriculum is predetermined subject matter to be delivered to students. All the works of curriculum are held at the central level. Teachers do not experience any works together with CDC.• It looks as if we are seeking just quantitative achievement of targeted instructional objectives. Objectives are not determined by seeing learner's capacity, need, interest and aspiration. |
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	Decentralized Curriculum Development Practice: Inclusive and Participatory
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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need of decentralized curriculum development practice so that it becomes inclusive and participatory. Policy encourages the right of every teacher has to participate in curriculum development process in policy. |
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	Teachers' Participation in Curriculum Development
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Inclusion on Teacher Participation

- The main user of curriculum is teacher so it is needed to enlarge the scope of teacher's participation in the curriculum development practice.
- Few teachers are incorporated in curriculum related work but not from local place.

Teacher as a mere implementer rather than Developer of Curriculum

- Teacher's role in curriculum development process is limited only to implement the written curricula.
- Teacher has a lot of experiences of classroom teaching and knowledge of daily lives of people. Teachers face several challenges and barriers of instructional practices everyday so incorporation of teacher's experiences, knowledge and skills makes the curriculum valuable and applicable to learners and their lives.

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Indeed we can say that teacher is the core person for curriculum development process. So respondents as core persons for this process have understood that in Nepal it is centralized in spite of the legal provision and policy of decentralization. NCF (2019) has stated curriculum as a process following the concept of decentralization to make it inclusive, participatory and practicable. Different literature, theory and study seek greater teacher participation in the curriculum development practices but as to say from the findings of this study it is impractical and almost centralized process. This study found that for inclusive and participatory curriculum development process greater role of local teachers is needed. Stenhouse (1975 as cited in Kelly, 2004) said that curriculum is a practical form of specification about the practice of teaching. It is not the package or syllabus of ground to be covered. From this assumption of curriculum we can see the central role of teacher in each and every phase of curricular process.

But this research indicates the role of teacher as mere implementer of curriculum. This indicates the hegemony of objective model of curriculum instead of process model of curriculum. This result indicates that there is clear demarcation between policy and practice in teacher participation in curriculum development process of Nepal.

Conclusion

It is noticed that a practice of curriculum development is centrally dominated in Nepal. Having said this, teachers' roles and responsibilities cannot be neglected but need to provide more prominent role for designing, developing, implementing, and evaluating the curriculum. From the participant's voices, it is found that teachers has not so prominent role for designing and developing the curriculum. Few teachers have such opportunity that lived in capital city. Theoretically participants were very much unaware to curriculum development process. They tried to understand and defined on their own way. They understand the curriculum development process as writing the draft curriculum. They perceived that it is the work of government. Their responsibility is only teaching the planned curriculum. After analyzing participants' understanding and perception about curriculum development process and its practice, it is conclude that teachers have lack of theoretical knowledge about curriculum development, practices of curriculum development process, and their participation.

From the literatures' review, existing polices and the data collected from the participants, it shows that the ownership of curriculum development process needs to be in real practitioners' hand that is teacher. Entire respondents had not got any opportunity to participate in curriculum

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development process. It seems that they have only the opportunity to participate in implementation and evaluation as being a teacher. They don't have any opportunity to participate in curriculum design, development and revision instead of the implementation of readymade curriculum and evaluate students' targeted performance.

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